

A RESEARCH REVIEW ON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF LIFE IN FOLK LITERATURE

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Abstract

word "KHALQI " means in Brahui language a person who belongs to rural, or called villager. so, the literature which is created by Brahui elders. Folk literature is the initial period of any literature, no one knows who are the creators of folk literature. literature has been Travelled orally from generation to generation. we find folksongs, stories, proverbs idioms, riddles and quotations. folk literature is the mirror image of any nation. Folk literature tells us about history, life style, customs and traditions, environment, thoughts, imagination and emotions of a nation. it is considered that the ancient language. so, its folk literature could be ancient. This research evaluates the Brahui folk literature. The researchers brought out the work on Brahui folk literature.

Keywords: Folk, Brahui, Literature, Traditions, Environment, Language.

Introduction

"Literature" is derived from the Arabic language and is used as a source in Urdu. The source of the word "literature" comes from adbaa (with the accent on dal), which means to be literate" and from that comes "adib" whose plural is adaba. If the source of the words (with jazm on dal) which means to prepare feast food and is used in the meaning of feast. Hence, the active noun is "manners". Literature is also spoken in the same sense, the meaning of which is also used in teaching knowledge. Both active and active come in the meaning of learning literature and being literate. The meaning of literature is respect for someone's greatness, dignity, respect, reverence, favorite method, code or etiquette, Qaida, Qarinah, etc.

Literature in Brahui language is called literature, like literature is prevalent in other languages of Pakistan. Literature is such a good practice due to which a person is characterized by better qualities. (Literature) is such knowledge through which one can convey his meaning to others through words and writings. And its subject is word and letter. Its advantage is the expression of ma in the pronoun.

No one can deny that Brahui is an ancient language, but the fact that, like other languages, Brahui literature has been relatively little worked on has its place. This deficiency or weakness can be said to be a sign of low knowledge in a nation or language, but it cannot destroy the tradition of that nation or language. One of the reasons why Brahui literature is not ancient like Brahui language and society is that the tribes of Brahui nation were mostly wasting their time in wars and bloodshed. For this reason, this nation stayed away from the path of knowledge and literature. One of the reasons has also been that the Brahui nation lacks endurance like other nations. This reason also kept him

away from knowledge and literature: As far as Brahui prose writing is concerned, Brahui folk stories have been traveling side by side for thousands of years, psychological, social and social aspects are visible in these stories. About which Dr. Abdul Rahman Brahui, the eminent scholar of Brahui, says: Stories reflect the entire society. In it, we get pictures of people's customs, manners and thoughts, (2,9 2014)

When did the story begin, Professor Susan has described its origin in his book Ancient Prose Literature. When man came into being on earth, he first learned to speak. When a hunter would reach his home after hunting from the forests, he would sit and narrate all his situations and events in front of his family in night gatherings, so the era of story-telling begins. That is why it is said that story-telling is as old as the language of man. Narrating an event with parts is called a story. Its oldest form is narrative. Greek scholars believe that story-telling is older than the goddesses of poetry and music. It can be said that our folk literature stories existed thousands of years ago. (Brahui Susan 2015: 21)

It shows that humans could communicate their ideas to each other and cooperate with each other.

There are stories in the literature of Brahui people that still need to be interpreted because they mention such powers, there are also some stories in which there are inhuman characters, there are some stories of people in which our civilized power, religious tolerance, social life. The economy, but our customs and traditions are also seen in them Folk literature is a social mirror of any nation. Its study reveals about their morals, culture, standing, sitting, ritual and economic resources. As the name of folk literature is evident, folk literature has emerged from the inhabitants of plains, mountains and desolate places. (Professor Susan 2014, 19)

Similarly, there is a whole world in proverbs and idioms as Munir Hanafi has said about proverbs. There are many proverbs in the language and literature, clever, wise people have made them after many years of experience and analysis. It has taken many years to make proverbs, there is no information about their makers, but people of all ages have preserved the words of these wise people. In the same way, he says about the allusions that these are also made after analysis and experience” (Hanafi 2013, 28).

Along with the creation of folk tales, proverbs and idioms were created. Which led our people to a conscious and straight path? Because proverbs and proverbs are the inherited things that describe the religion, life and history of any nation.

Thus, the first ones are also made for mental testing. So that he can tell his people the boundaries of his area and create mental expansion and awareness. In our language there are many firsts. From stories, proverbs and sayings, people started writing poetry to keep themselves happy because poetry was made to keep people happy. Zouk Brahui has written about it like this;

Brahui have been inheritors of this land for thousands of years. At that time, they laid the foundation of this great culture. The mountains of this land have been listening to the sweet dialect of Brahui language for thousands of years. Brahui folk poetry contains true and complete stories of thought and action and it shows the reality of life. It gives us the motivation to live, our culture and the quality of our national identity. (Brahui Zouk 2023-22)

Thus, when our shepherd is with his flock, he expresses his thoughts about life in the form of poetry. Make some way of living. There is special help in knowing the life in all those things from which customs and customs came into being. This social life makes us different from the people of other languages with the help of folk literature, the ideas of any nation can be found about the culture, civilization, living conditions and customs. It is as expressed in folk tales, proverbs and idioms and

in social life as practices in the form of its beautiful customs and beliefs Folk tales are far from reality, they have all kinds of characters. Brahui folktales have some imaginative characters which are not found in folktales of other languages. The earliest stories of folk tales are mostly from the hunting period which reflect the life of that period. Then gradually human life expanded.

About this, Prof. Dr. Manzoor Baloch explains one of his articles the reasons for the lack of criticism in Brahui literature; "Where these early stories came into existence, the colors of the methods began to be added to the region as well." Gradually, thoughts and thoughts increased in them. In this way, false stories and false stories were added to the stories. The stories gradually took on a religious color in the court of U Nan Vroom, which included the role of the hero. In this way, completely different human stories of nature began to be told. However, the stories of the fictional world are still included with them. (Manzoor Baloch 2010)

Apart from this, people get information about ways of living in stories and folk literature, environment, customs, civilization, culture, thought and livelihood. As after reading Brahui folk stories we get information about the royal life of our people. In them, love, friendship, enmity, employment issues, lifestyle, nomadic relationships, occasions of trouble and happiness, advice of elders, solidarity, wealth, sorrow, happiness, all aspects are evident in them.

In a similar vein, Vizier Yousuf Rodini writes about folk tales Literature begins with a story. The history of story and story-telling is as old as the history of human existence. As if the story and story-telling begin with human existence. (Rodini 2015).

Thus, we can say that man has been a master of storytelling since day one. In the same way, the Brahui nation is basically Muslim, so all its rituals and customs, be they happy or sad, are all in accordance with Islamic teachings.

Result

Folk literature itself is the first history of any nation which reflects the entire life and social affairs of the nation. Folk literature is the oldest form of life of any nation. In this way, folk literature is a picture of a nation's traditions, values and culture. It is also true that folk literature is one of the ancient signs of any nation, which tells about the beginning of life. The purpose of folk literature is to create ethnic and cultural unity among the people of a nation and language. Through it, our elders used to describe the laws and rules, which were supposed to be followed by every tribe. Folk literature gives moral lessons to the coming generations, then it conveys our cultural values to the new generation. The ancient language of a nation can be preserved through folk literature. Folk literature is a sign of unity and disunity. Any language in the world It begins with folk literature. Folk literature, poetry or stories and proverbs and allusions are said to be the most valuable among all literary genres. Through folk literature, any national social problems are revealed. Our folk literature is a mirror of our social life. Through folk literature, our social life and customs are described in a much better way.

All aspects of social life can be seen in the folk literature. The status of social life in Brahui folk literature is such that Brahui society is a conscious society. Their folk stories or people in poetry or proverbs and allusions describe their social life. It looks very clear. Just as people's literature sees the many problems of our society, social indifference and poverty, in the same way, the lack of education and economic weakness of the Brahui society also describes the war, cruelty and indifference of the chiefs If we look at the social life of the Brahui people, they have been nomads. They have spent their lives in hard work. Livestock and agriculture have been the means of livelihood of the Brahui nation. That is why they have taken hard work to live. In every aspect of folk literature,

there are ways of living, rituals, a special way of thinking, tribal influences, Sukh Khan Khanate, conflict and war between each other.

So, this proves that folk literature itself is a reality. The evidence of folk literature being close to reality is proved after reading our proverbs and sayings that they are made after experience and analysis. Regarding the sustainability of folk literature, I think that more work is needed on the works that have been done so far, but folk literature still exists among the nomadic people, for which there is a great need for research so that folk literature Be safe for future generations.

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